

BUILDING BRIDGES THROUGH LANGUAGE: ENHANCING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *Intercultural communicative competence (ICC) has become a crucial aspect of foreign language teaching and learning. Language and culture are deeply interconnected, with culture being expressed through language. Therefore, learning a new language without understanding its cultural context is incomplete. Today, English speakers face two significant challenges: adapting to global cultures and effectively representing their local culture in comparison to others. This study aims to investigate the lived experiences of university-level English teachers in promoting intercultural communication within English Language Teaching (ELT) classrooms. Using a qualitative research approach, the study adopts an interpretive paradigm and phenomenological design. Four English language teachers from the central campus of Far Western University served as participants. Data were collected through in-depth interviews and personal narratives. The findings indicate that the participants view the promotion of intercultural communication positively, both in fostering global cultural understanding and in highlighting local cultural identities. The proposed tasks are versatile and adaptable to various learning contexts, addressing students' specific needs and interests. They integrate the four language skills and simultaneously emphasize communicative and intercultural competencies. By fostering these abilities, the tasks aim to develop learners into effective mediators in the foreign language teaching and learning process.*

Keywords: *multicultural environments, language learning, intercultural communication, cultural identities.*

As global interactions increase, the demand for intercultural communication skills is growing, especially in multilingual and multicultural environments. In an increasingly globalized world, businesses and individuals recognize the importance of understanding cultural differences to avoid communication barriers, confusion, and misunderstandings when interacting in foreign contexts. Intercultural communication plays a crucial role in building and maintaining relationships by bridging cultural gaps.

Culture is not static; it is constantly evolving as groups negotiate and redefine their norms and values. Language, being the primary medium through which culture is expressed, is integral to foreign language teaching and learning. While factual information is important, developing cultural awareness fosters critical thinking and deeper understanding. To effectively engage in intercultural communication within foreign language learning, it is essential to understand the concept of culture and acquire the skills to navigate diverse cultural contexts.

Defining intercultural competence is a complex task. At the heart of intercultural competence is the preparation of individuals to interact appropriately and effectively with those from other cultural backgrounds (Sincope et al., 2012). As a result, understanding culture becomes an integral component of intercultural competence. Nieto's (1999) definition of culture as, "...the ever-changing values, traditions, social and political relationships, and worldview created, shared, and transformed by a group of people. . ." (p.48) makes it difficult to identify

which aspects of a given culture should be included in classroom instruction. Furstenberg (2010b) further explains that, "...culture is a highly complex, elusive, multilayered notion that encompasses many different and overlapping areas and that inherently defies easy categorization and classification" (p. 329).

Language is a fundamental factor in intercultural communication, particularly in the context of foreign language learning and teaching. While students often learn the rules and structures of a language, they may still struggle with effective communication if they lack knowledge of the target culture. Without an understanding of cultural nuances, students may find it difficult to apply their language skills appropriately in real-life situations.

Therefore, it is essential that students are introduced to the cultural context of the language they are learning from the outset. This cultural awareness helps bridge the gap between linguistic knowledge and practical communication, enabling students to engage more effectively in intercultural exchanges and fully comprehend the language's usage in diverse cultural settings.

The concept of culture has always been intricate, as it is reflected in various patterns of language, thought, and behavior, which can vary across different ethnic groups, geographic locations, and worldviews. In 1976, Hall introduced the iceberg analogy to describe culture. He proposed that culture, like an iceberg, has visible aspects above the waterline, such as behaviors and certain beliefs, while a much larger portion lies hidden beneath the surface. The visible elements represent the external, conscious aspects of culture, while the hidden portion encompasses deeper beliefs, values, and thought patterns that shape behavior. This analogy emphasizes that we cannot fully understand a culture based only on its outward signs; instead, we must invest time in learning about the people and the deeper cultural elements that influence their behavior.

Effective communication across cultures is crucial for numerous aspects of life. In the business world, it enables companies to expand their global presence and form partnerships with clients and customers from diverse cultural backgrounds. For travelers, intercultural communication enhances the experience by fostering meaningful connections with locals and providing a richer understanding of different cultures. In diplomacy, it plays a vital role in promoting international cooperation, resolving conflicts, and building mutual understanding through respectful dialogue. Overall, the ability to communicate effectively across cultures is indispensable for fostering collaboration, improving relationships, and achieving success in a globalized world.

Kirkpatrick (2007: 5-15) distinguishes the sociolinguistic and linguistic dimensions of World Englishes, sub-categorizing the former as follows:

1. Native varieties vs. nativized varieties vs. lingua franca Englishes;
2. The native speaker vs. the non-native speaker;
3. The functions of language and the identity-communication continuum;
4. Linguistic prejudice

One of the biggest challenges in preparing students for intercultural competence is evaluating and measuring their progress in this area. Given that each student comes to the classroom with unique perspectives and worldviews, it is nearly impossible to expect all students to develop intercultural skills at the same pace.

Developing intercultural competence requires more than just understanding surface-level customs and traditions; it involves exploring the historical, social, and political contexts that shape

a culture. By gaining a deeper understanding of these factors, individuals can foster authentic connections rooted in mutual respect and appreciation. This reduces the potential for misunderstandings or conflicts arising from cultural differences and enables individuals to navigate cultural nuances with greater sensitivity and adaptability. As a result, intercultural competence helps build trust, strengthen relationships, and establish rapport across cultural boundaries, creating more harmonious and productive interactions.

The variety of definitions and interpretations of intercultural competence reflects the different contexts in which American citizens are encouraged to develop cross-cultural understanding. As interactions with people from other countries become more common, intercultural competence is increasingly seen as essential. The idea of preparing globally aware students who recognize the interconnectedness of today's world is also gaining attention in K-12 education discussions. Byram (1997) outlines intercultural competence as involving interactions with people from other cultures while using one's native language, or interpreting documents translated from another culture or language. In this case, understanding or speaking a foreign language is not required. On the other hand, intercultural communicative competence includes self-awareness, inquiry, and process, but it also emphasizes the importance of using a foreign language to engage effectively in intercultural exchanges.

A native English speaker may overlook grammatical or phonological errors made by an EFL speaker, but cultural missteps are often less tolerated and can lead to significant communication breakdowns. Therefore, incorporating English culture into EFL teaching and syllabi is essential for developing proficient users of English who can communicate effectively and appropriately with native speakers. Understanding English culture also encourages students to think critically about both English culture and their own. An effective approach to teaching the language is to use materials that make the content relatable and familiar to learners.

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